

VNF Placement over Autonomic Elastic Optical Network via Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Orchestration of computing and network resources across multiple technology layers is critical for the autonomous roll-out of network services that fulfill the heterogeneous requirements of vertical industries. Therefore, effectively mapping the requirements of verticals into underlying infrastructure management decisions is a challenging issue. In this paper, we evaluated the provisioning of vertical-driven network services, composed of a set of interconnected virtual network functions, on top of a distributed cloud infrastructure interconnected through an Elastic Optical Network (EON). To this end, we propose a solution exploiting the advantages of Deep Reinforcement Learning. This solution relies on two cooperating agents to execute an efficient selection of computing resources in the cloud infrastructure for the placement of virtualized network functions, as well as the routing and spectrum assignment in the EON. The performance of the proposed solution is evaluated in scenarios where arrival and departure of service requests are dynamic. Experimental results show the improved performance of the proposed solution with and without invalid action masking over a heuristic algorithm in terms of service blocking rate.

Index Terms—Network Function Virtualization, Elastic Optical Networks, Deep Reinforcement Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of *network slicing* enables flexible and dynamic provisioning of network services entailing the mapping of heterogeneous high-level requirements demanded by vertical services (e.g., Industry4.0, automotive, etc.) onto low-level compute and networking resources. In this context, both Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Software Defined Networking (SDN) concepts appear as the key enablers [1]. Specifically, NFV and SDN allow the creation of tailored virtual networks on top of a common shared physical infrastructure that meet the specific service and resource needs of each vertical service. A network slice/service consists of a set of Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) that can be distributed geographically in several cloud sites/data centers. Therefore, the provisioning of such services entails the selection and allocation of both computational and network resources that meet the requirements of the VNFs (i.e., CPU, RAM, storage) and the links (e.g., bandwidth and latency) interconnecting those

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VNFs. This problem, commonly referred to as VNF placement, has been notably addressed from different approaches. A traditional approach considers that a network service/slice is modeled as a service function chain (SFC). An SFC is an ordered sequence of VNFs, where traffic traverses the VNFs in a predefined and sequential order. However, realistic network services can require more complex representations than a *linear* VNF connectivity, which results in meshed VNF interconnections. In general, such VNF interconnections are called VNF Forwarding Graphs (VNF-FGs), where the SFC is one option. The SFC placement problem has been well studied in the literature, which is an NP-hard problem [2]. Thus, since VNF-FG placement (with meshed VNF topology) is much more complex than the SFC placement problem, it is also NP-hard [3].

Thanks to its offered high transmission capacity and efficient use of the optical spectrum, Elastic Optical Networks (EON) are the most promising transport network technology for the data center/cloud site interconnections [4]. EON can allocate just enough optical spectrum resources through a finer and more flexible allocation of the wavelength channels tailored to accommodate heterogeneous bandwidth needs (e.g., 10, 40, 100, 400 Gb/s).

Computing and network resources need to be effectively allocated over an infrastructure formed by distributed cloud sites connected through a transport EON for the deployment of NFV-based services. Several approaches to VNF placement have been proposed in the literature ranging from optimization problem solving to heuristics and machine learning (ML) [5]–[9]. Among ML techniques, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has recently received more attention because learning is performed by direct interaction with the system environment. This brings some advantages such as the absence of an initial training dataset and capturing the dynamic behavior of the system (e.g., the stochastic arrival of diverse service requests). Additionally, DRL can handle high-dimensional underlying network states and VNF placement actions, which is not the case for solving optimization problems (usually formulated as Integer Linear Programming) which do not scale well when applied to large-scale networks or high dynamic network service arrival [8]. Importantly, DRL considers the long-term performance of the system through its *discount factor*, which reflects the impact that decisions have on long-term performance. This differs from other adopted solutions

based on heuristics which only focus on the immediate/current system performance [9]. In [8], the VNF-FG placement is tackled through a DRL-based solution that combines both DRL technique with a heuristic algorithm. The proposed algorithm enhances the exploration of the DRL agent. While the paper deals with VNF-FG placement, it does not tackle that the underlying transport network is based on an EON which does impose stringent optical spectrum constraints. Similarly, a DRL-based method to deal with VNF-FG placement is presented in [10]. That work exploits the graph structure of the VNF-FG and the substrate network by leveraging graph neural networks to embed the state information. Nevertheless, the specific technological requirements of optical networks are neglected. In [11], the authors apply DRL to solve a multi-objective SFC placement problem that considers a wavelength division multiplexing optical network for the data center interconnection. Although the wavelength continuity constraint of the optical network is considered, the network services to be provisioned are simply represented as linear VNFs interconnections (SFC). Finally, an SFC placement approach based on DRL is proposed in [9] where the reward is formulated tied to key factors such as QoE and QoS requirements.

Herein, we propose a novel DRL-based approach for the dynamic network service provisioning on top of a distributed cloud infrastructure connected by a transport EON. The solution is composed of two cooperating DRL agents to find the best policy for selecting the data centers to host VNFs and the optical connections (*lightpaths*) interconnecting them. The novelty of the work stems from the following contributions:

- A VNF placement solution based on DRL for a realistic scenario is proposed, where service requests (1) are represented as complex meshed topologies rather than simpler SFCs; and (2) arrive and depart dynamically.
- The devised solution leverages two DRL agents. The first agent computes the best lightpath between a pair of data centers considering the available optical spectrum and latency. The second agent exploits the information inferred by the first agent to build a VNF placement policy, which means selecting the best data center that will accommodate a VNF without violating the computational requirements and connection constraints between VNFs. Thus, our solution jointly considers the computing resources available in the data center and the unused spectrum resources in the underlying optical network.
- To train the DRL agent, we constructed a VNF placement environment compatible with OpenAI Gym [12] and used two different DRL algorithms with and without *invalid action masking*. The performance of the DRL-based algorithms is benchmarked against a heuristic algorithm in terms of network service blocking rate.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A cloud and transport EON network infrastructure with distributed data centers is considered. The data centers offer compute resources (i.e., CPU, RAM, and storage) to host the VNFs of every incoming network service. The EON is

composed of fiber optical links and switching nodes, i.e., Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (ROADMs). All the lightpaths to be set up, between a pair of data centers, are subject to the fulfillment of spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints. That is, the lightpath allocates the same optical spectrum (i.e., central frequency channel and frequency slot) on each link forming the optical path. Given this scenario, the goal is to dynamically select and provision incoming network service requests fulfilling their requirements, i.e., computing and networking resources (e.g., CPU, RAM, bandwidth, etc.) and satisfying QoS demands (e.g., maximum latency).

This work aligns with the ETSI NFV architecture [13]. In a nutshell, this consists of three main functional blocks: (1) the Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) encompassing the physical cloud/network infrastructure and the required virtualization software; (2) the VNF instances that run on the top of the NFVI; and (3) the Management and Orchestration (MANO) handling and coordinating underlying controllers for the deployment of network services within the NFVI. Specifically, within the NFV MANO, three architectural blocks are identified: NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), VNF Manager (VNFM), and Virtualised Infrastructure Manager (VIM). A network service is defined by a template termed a Network Service Descriptor (NSD) [14]. This template determines the list of VNFs to be deployed, and the VNF-FG that defines the connections between them through virtual links (VL). The NSD also describes the operational requirements for the VNFs (e.g. required CPU, memory, storage) and VLs (e.g. minimum latency, maximum latency).

Upon receiving a service request from a pool of predefined request types, denoted by $NS = \{ns_1, \dots, ns_{|NS|}\}$, the NFVO triggers a placement algorithm to select the cloud and network resources that do fulfill the requirements. The placement algorithm uses as inputs the current resource availability, typically reported by dedicated controllers: VIMs for the cloud resources and WAN Infrastructure Manager (WIM) for the transport network [5]. Thereby, each VIM controller managing a particular cloud site (i.e., Point of Presence, PoP) communicates with the NFVO to report the PoP computing resource status (e.g., aggregated amount of unused CPU, memory and storage). The transport EON resource information is reported by the WIM controller (e.g., SDN controller). As said, the output of the placement algorithm successfully accommodating a network service is formed by: i) the set of PoPs to deploy the VNFs; and ii) the transport resources (lightpaths) enabling the communication among the PoPs. With this information, then the NFVO coordinates with the corresponding VIMs to instantiate the targeted VNFs. Likewise, the deployment of VLs (between VNFs) over the transport EON is managed by the WIM. If either compute resources in the PoPs or the transport networking requirements cannot be met, the service is blocked.

The substrate physical network is modeled as a directed graph $G(N, L)$, where N is a set of optical switching nodes with PoPs attached and L is a set of optical links. Each PoP is characterized by its computing, memory and storage

Fig. 1. VNF-FG placement over a multilayer network.

capacities. The set of available PoP resources is denoted by $C = \{C_{cpu}, C_{mem}, C_{hdd}\}$. Similarly, each link $l(u, v) \in L$ interconnecting a pair of optical nodes $u, v \in N$ is described as $\{B, D\}$, where B represents the available transmission capacity in terms of frequency slots (FSs) and D is the communication latency.

Each network service request is modeled as a VNF-FG i.e., a directed graph $G_V(N_V, L_V)$. Note that N_V represents a set of interconnected VNFs and L_V represents the virtual links between VNFs. Each $n_V \in N_V$ has a demand of resources denoted by $R = \{R_{cpu}, R_{mem}, R_{hdd}\}$. Similarly, each virtual link $l_V \in L_V$ has a bandwidth demand B_V and latency constraint D_V . Moreover, the substrate network path that supports a virtual link is denoted as $P(L_V) = \{l_1, \dots, l_n\}; l_n \in L$. This path represents the lightpath that interconnects a PoP pair.

Figure 1 shows the complete process of VNF-FG placement over the aforementioned scenario for a service request demanding 4 VNFs. The interconnections between VNFs are: $VNF_1 \leftrightarrow VNF_2$, $VNF_1 \leftrightarrow VNF_3$, $VNF_2 \leftrightarrow VNF_3$, $VNF_2 \leftrightarrow VNF_4$, and $VNF_3 \leftrightarrow VNF_4$. Following the results of the placement algorithm, VNFs are mapped as follows: VNF_1 to PoP_1 , VNF_2 to PoP_2 , and both VNF_3 and VNF_4 to PoP_3 . Each PoP is equipped with a set of optical transceivers. An optical transceiver provides: (1) the required optical transmission capabilities (e.g., generation of the optical signal at a given central frequency and occupying a specific FS); (2) the coherent reception of an optical channel. Thus, electrical-optical and optical-electrical conversions are intrinsically realized at the transceivers to enable data processing at each VNF (red dotted lines). In addition, it is also necessary to calculate lightpaths (blue solid lines) between the selected PoPs that support the virtual link requirements (blue dotted line) such as bandwidth, latency, etc. In the example, observe that VNF_3 and VNF_4 are hosted in the same PoP and thus, no lightpath needs to be set up.

III. DEEP REINFORCEMENT LEARNING APPROACH

This section presents the design and implementation of the DRL solution for VNF-FG placement. The building blocks of the solution and the interaction between them are elaborated. The DRL agents' implementation details are then presented.

As mentioned in Section II, after receiving a service request, a placement algorithm is triggered. This algorithm aims to select the PoPs that meet the computational requirements and the network resources to roll out the lightpaths between each pair of selected PoPs. Unlike solutions that rely on preset rules, our solution is based on two DRL agents, one devoted to computing the best lightpath between PoPs, and a second one that chooses the PoPs for hosting network service VNFs. The former agent is a DRL-based routing and spectrum allocation (RSA) mechanism that jointly considers the spectrum utilization of the optical links and the delay constraint of the service requesting the lightpath. We proposed this DRL agent in [15]. Hereafter we refer to the first agent as Path-DRL agent and the second agent as Compute-DRL agent. A detailed description of the Compute-DRL agent is presented below.

For each service request, the Compute-DRL agent iterates over every $n_V \in N_V$, trying to place it into a PoP. The Compute-DRL agent takes as *input state* the VNF requirements consisting of: (1) the demand vector of resources R of the VNF n_V ; and (2) the latency D_V and bandwidth B_V constraints of the virtual links l_V . Additional inputs for the Compute-DRL are: the available computing resources C in every PoP and the latency of the best lightpaths $P(L_V)$ interconnecting every pair of PoPs. Notice that these lightpaths must fulfill the required bandwidth demand B_V of the virtual links l_V . The agent outputs the selected PoP as *action*.

Regarding the *reward*, once a VNF is successfully allocated, the agent will receive a reward of 0. In the case that the network service (its VNF-FG) is fully deployed, the reward is equal to the aggregate computing capacity (i.e. CPU, memory and storage) successfully allocated. This leads to encourage the rollout of the complete network services. On the other hand, if a VNF cannot be deployed because the constraints and requirements cannot be met, the reward will be negative.

Figure 2 summarizes the design of the devised DRL-based solution. In short, the Path-DRL agent computes the *best* candidate lightpaths (i.e., nodes, links and FSs) that jointly meet the bandwidth and latency demands of the network service's virtual links. Recall that these lightpaths do ensure that both spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints are met. The selection of the *best* candidate paths considers the link spectrum features (i.e., available FSs), the number of FSs required for a request (based on the virtual link bandwidth needs), as well as the required virtual latency to be fulfilled by the accumulated lightpath delay. Further details can be found in [15]. On the other hand, the Compute-DRL agent selects the PoPs that satisfy both the computational requirements of the VNFs and the latency and bandwidth requirements of the virtual links. Note that the latter needs the output of the Path-DRL agent, i.e. the set of lightpaths between every pair of

Fig. 2. DRL-based solution for VNF-FG Placement.

PoPs attached to the optical nodes. Thus, at each iteration of the Path-DRL agent, the best lightpaths are computed and then exposed to the Compute-DRL agent.

Algorithm 1 NS provisioning

- 1: Initialize environment
- 2: **for** ns in NS **do**
- 3: **for** n_V in N_V **do**
- 4: $pop \leftarrow selectPoP(C, D, B_V, D_V, P(L_V))$
- 5: **if** pop satisfies B_V, D_V constraints **then**
- 6: Allocate the compute resources for n_V
- 7: Allocate the network resources for l_v
- 8: **else**
- 9: Reject ns
- 10: Release allocated resources
- 11: **break**
- 12: **end if**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **end for**

The key steps of the network service (NS) provisioning process are shown in Algorithm 1. This algorithm is the basis for both the offline training process and the online provisioning process. In offline training, these steps need to be performed for a certain number of training episodes until the reward converges to a maximum value. The parameters of the neural networks used by the DRL agent are periodically updated after a fixed number of training episodes. DRL agent training relies on a tuple formed of the current and next state, the action and the reward stored in an experience buffer. After the training process, a trained model is obtained, allowing the online network service provisioning. The trained model can quickly perform the optimal PoP selection to host VNFs in compliance with computational and network constraints.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Compute DRL Agent Implementation

To train the DRL agent, we first developed an environment that follows the OpenAI Gym guidelines to tackle the RSA problem in EONs as well as the allocation of computing resources in PoPs. This environment allows the integration with

Fig. 3. Substrate infrastructure: NSFNET topology with optical link delays.

state-of-the-art RL implementations, such as Stable Baselines 3 [16]. These implementations require the definition of the action and observation spaces, the reward, the definition of an episode, and the subsequent steps for each action executed in the environment.

The DRL agent is implemented based on the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [17] and PPO with invalid action masking [18] (Maskable PPO) algorithms. We leveraged RL algorithms implementation of Stable Baseline 3. We set the learning rate to 10^{-5} and the discount factor to 0.95. The batch size is 256. The agent also features neural networks with five fully connected hidden layers and 128 neurons on each layer. The input observation space is defined as a dictionary that consists of: the available PoP compute resources, the lightpath delay interconnecting each pair of PoPs, the requested compute resources and the required delay. The output action space was defined as a discrete action specifying the selected PoPs and consequently the lightpaths to interconnect them.

B. Simulation Settings

The simulation experiments were performed using the NSFNet topology formed by 14 nodes and 42 links as substrate infrastructure. Since VNFs primarily use CPU computational power [9], in this work, we focus on the CPU as a resource to allocate. Each node has attached a PoP with a CPU capacity of 100 units (i.e., CPU cores). Each optical fiber link offers 100 FSs (with an assumed spectrum granularity of 6.25GHz). The link delays, in ms, are labelled in Fig. 3. The network services are dynamically generated and terminated. The arrival of the requests follows a Poisson process, whilst the lifetime of a successfully deployed network service follows an exponential distribution. While the inter-arrival time is set to a fixed value, the lifetime is varied to produce different loads. Three descriptors modelling three network service types were defined to mimic different verticals with heterogeneous computational (i.e. VNFs) and network (i.e., VLs) requirements. The number of VNFs per network service type, the set of VLs and their needs (bandwidth and latency) are shown in Table I. The generated network services are chosen uniformly from these predefined types. The CPU demand of each VNF is evenly distributed among [1, 5, 10].

We compare the performance of our Compute-DRL agent with the Non-Recursive Greedy SFC Placement (NGSP) algorithm [9]. NGSP deploys the VNFs over PoPs that present the maximum available resources as long as the bandwidth

TABLE I
NSD TYPES

Vertical (NSD type)	# of VNFs	# of VLs	Bandwidth (FSs)	Latency (ms)
Industry 4.0	2	2	2	5
Automotive	4	10	4	10
Media	6	20	8	15

Fig. 4. Offline Training Process.

and latency requirements of the virtual links are not violated. The lightpaths supporting the virtual links are computed using a k-shortest path algorithm using the first-fit heuristic for the FS selection.

C. Experimental Results

1) *Convergence of Compute-DRL Agent in Training Process:* To train our DRL agent, we applied a technique known as *invalid action masking* [18]. This technique reduces the action space by removing invalid actions in a given state of the environment. From the current state of the environment, it is possible to know which actions are invalid. For example in our environment, all PoPs that have a computational capacity less than the required by a VNF represent invalid actions and therefore, they should be removed from the action space. Figure 4 shows the training curves for our DRL agent using PPO algorithm without and with invalid action masking (Maskable PPO). Here, an episode consists of the provisioning of 5000 network services. As depicted in Fig. 4, Maskable PPO converges faster than PPO, 2.8 and 3.6 million episodes, respectively; reducing the training time by roughly 1 hour. This learning process took approximately 2 hours on a Linux server equipped with 1 x Intel Xeon CPU E5-2603v4 (1.70GHz, 12 cores and 30MB cache) and 64GB of RAM. It can also be observed that the average reward of the PPO masking algorithm is higher than that of the PPO. This means that more service requests have been successfully deployed since a positive reward is only given when a complete service is deployed. Then, the trained model is used to perform the online provisioning of network services.

2) *Comparison of Network Service Blocking:* The metric used to compare the performance of our agent is the network service blocking rate. This accounts for the ratio between the number of blocked (not deployed) services and the total number of requests. Thereby, the lower the blocking rate, the

Fig. 5. NS Blocking for NGSP, PPO and Maskable PPO

better the solution performs. A service is blocked due to the lack of either computing or network resources.

Figure 5 presents the service blocking when provisioning 5000 network services using the NGSP algorithm and the Compute-DRL agent trained with PPO and Maskable PPO. This process was repeated 10 times. Note that, our agent clearly outperforms (i.e., obtains lower blocking) NGSP regardless of the RL algorithm used or the requests load. For instance, under 50 Erlangs of requests load, the blocking rate obtained from the agent trained with Maskable PPO attains the best performance, reducing the blocking by 12.8% compared to that of the NGSP algorithm. In other words, this proposed agent leads to about 640 more requests being successfully deployed. The Maskable PPO slightly reduces the blocking rate by 0.6% compared to the agent trained with PPO, representing 30 more successfully deployed network services. The reason for this slight improvement is that without invalid action masking, the agent can choose PoPs without enough resources to host a VNF. Therefore, the agent trained with PPO must learn during the training process to identify PoPs that are not eligible, using a negative reward. Conversely, in the case of Maskable PPO, the agent can learn very early on which are the feasible PoPs, allowing the agent to learn a solution with higher performance.

Furthermore, in Fig. 6 the blocking cause/reason (i.e., compute or network violations) is shown. The main cause of blocking a network service is the lack of computational resources to allocate VNFs. In light of the results, it is observed that regardless of the load, the DRL approach always reduces the blocking caused by the lack of computing resources. This means that the DRL achieves a better VNF placement. Consequently, the overall blocking performance is enhanced by the DRL approach when compared to baseline NGSP.

3) *Impact of Number of VNFs per Network Service Type:* To evaluate the effect of the number of VNFs per network service type on the performance of the DRL agent, we performed simulations changing the initial settings of our experimental scenario. In this section, the number of VNFs per network service type is set to 2, 4 or 6 for all the generated service requests. We also conducted simulations varying the latency required by the network service. Figure 7 depicts the

Fig. 6. Causes of NS Blocking.

Fig. 7. Impact of Number of VNFs per VNF-FG.

accumulated network service blocking rate stating its cause.

From Fig. 7, it can be seen that by increasing the number of VNFs the network service blocking ratio grows (i.e., gets worse). Indeed, a higher number of VNFs implies a higher complexity of the topologies of the requested service. Thereby, not only more computational resources need to be allocated for the VNFs, but also more network resources are needed to accommodate the VLs. For the network service type with 2 VNFs, the service deployment failures caused by not meeting the virtual link demands are only observed when a very strict (lowest) delay requirement is needed. By contrast, for service types with 6 VNFs, the request rejections occur even with relaxed delay requirements. Moreover, with stringent delay requirements, the predominant cause of blocking is associated with the virtual links' needs. Whereas, with moderate latency requirements, the service rejection is mainly due to the lack of computational resources in the PoPs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a solution for the autonomous provisioning of network services over a cloud and transport network infrastructure, consisting of distributed PoPs interconnected through an EON. The solution considers services with complex/meshed VNF interconnection topologies and addresses the VNF placement problem by exploiting two DRL agents. The agents interact with each other to accomplish an optimal solution that considers both the computing and the network (optical spectrum) resources. One of the agents computes the

best lightpaths between a pair of PoPs. Computed lightpath attributes (e.g., incurred delay) are then used as input by the other agent to select the PoPs to host service VNFs.

The experimental results show that our DRL-based solution significantly outperforms the baseline NGSP algorithm by reducing the number of blocked services. This is achieved thanks to the tight cooperation between both DRL agents. Each agent focuses on solving one problem (spectrum assignment and compute allocation, respectively), and the output of one agent is the input for training the other. In addition, through the use of invalid action masking, it is shown that training time was reduced. The application of novel techniques such as invalid action masking and the use of cooperating agents for disaggregated functions results in a potential solution for simplifying complex problems such as the optimal selection of network and compute resources simultaneously.

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